

Youth and Human Rights - A Research Study among University Student

Mehul Rabari¹

Asst. Professor, ILSASS College, CVM, affiliated Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar

Dr. S. D. Mishra²

I/c Director, Department of Social Work, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar

Abstract: This Study has covered Post Graduate Students of four University of Gujarat State including Sardar Patel University, M. S. University, Gujarat University and DDIT University. The data collected from 400 P G Students 100 students from each university for the study under the research design of descriptive cum exploratory in nature. The Questionnaire is used for this research consists of 50 Questions. As a Consideration of that the youth or students are the future for any nation so level of understanding of youth about human rights is very important to know. If human rights knowledge is not up to mark among youth or students, it's a serious issue for the youth and nation as well. As a Social Worker, to maintain equality, non discrimination, protection and development is a mission. So, Human Rights is a one of the best weapon to all social worker to achieve main goals as mentioned before.

INTRODUCTION

Human beings are born equal in dignity, development and rights. These are moral claims which are natural in all individuals by virtue of their humanity alone, irrespective of caste, class, colour, creed, and place of birth, gender, cultural difference or any other consideration. These claims are made and formulated in what is today known as human rights. Human rights are sometimes known as fundamental rights, basic rights, inherent rights, natural rights and birth rights.

Hominine rights are standard rights and freedoms that all people are entitled to disregarding of nationality, sexuality, categorize, caste, soul or ethnic extraction, contend, religion, module, or other status. Anthropoid rights comprise civil and governmental rights, such as the rightish to aliveness, independency and freedom of language; and gregarious, cultural and system rights including the hand to move in civilization, the rightish to substance, and the just to operate and find an teaching. Fallible rights hold Rights (UDHR) is the fundament of the worldwide group of imposition for hominine rights. It had adopted by the Coalesced Nations Head Building on December 10th, 1948. This day is glorious annually as International Anthropomorphic Rights Day. The 30 articles of the UDHR plant the polite, governmental, system, party, and ethnical rights of all fill. It is a goal for imperfect lordliness that transcends political boundaries and permission, committing governments to reassert the basic rights of apiece person.

Results of the Study:

For this Study, Both male and female of the respondents are equal i.e. 50.0% (n=200).

Here, Researcher has tried to collect data equally male and female so that the opinion of both male and female understand and knowledge can include equally. And involvement of both gender can be helpful to get output in the proper way about of knowledge and understanding of human rights.

Majority of the respondent i.e. 79.5% (n=318) are unmarried, 17.7% (n=71) respondents are married and 2.7% (n=11) are divorcee respondents.

The marital status is very important one variable which effect on the opinion of respondent on the understanding and knowledge of human rights. Because the married and divorcee persons have more knowledge of human rights compare to unmarried persons. They believe their rights like right to live, right to marry, right to freedom of religion etc.

Majority of the respondent i.e. 56.0% (n=224) are lived in single unit of family and 44.0% (n=176) respondents are lived in joint family.

Family is the old institutions Indian society and they are pioneer institute who worked for the socialization of a human beings. Due to advent of industrialization and globalization nuclear family is on increasing trend hence it does effect on knowledge of individual with reference to rights of human being. It has been found from the above data that majority of respondents are from nuclear family hence one can say that substitute of knowledge would be either friends or educational institute.

Majority of respondents i.e. 74.5% (n=298) believe the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was Adopted by UNO on 10th December, 1948 where 15.0% (n=60) respondents don't believe the same and 10.5% (n=42) respondents are undecided. So, Researcher understood that majority around 75% of students aware that when UDHR had adopted by UNO but still many 25% of them are not aware the same.

Hence, it can be said that youth are believe about the inception of UNDH. This can be also analysed that about human rights youth are being believe about the organization who does work on policy formulation. Many authors also viewed in their study that youth are if don't believe about the organization that means they are not updated with recent trends of the human rights.

Majority of respondents i.e. 72.7% (n=291) don't believe that there is no provision for free and compulsory elementary education in India Constitution where 18.2% (n=73) respondents believe the same and 9.0% (n=36) respondents are undecided. So, Researcher understood that majority around 73% of students aware that there is provision for free and compulsory elementary

education in Indian Constitution but still many around 27% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 56.0% (n=224) believe that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights contains 30 Articles where 22.7% (n=91) respondents don't believe the same and 20.5% (n=85) respondents are undecided the same.

So, Researcher understood that majority 56% of students aware that UDHR contains 30 Articles but still many 44% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 66.0% (n=264) don't believe that the Preamble of Indian Constitution does not include human rights where 20.0% (n=80) respondents believe the same and 14.0% (n=56) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 66% of students aware that the Preamble of Indian Constitution include human rights but still many around 34% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 75.7% (n=303) believe that Human Rights have been included in the India Constitution in the form of fundamental rights and directive principles of State policy where 16.2% (n=65) respondents don't believe the same and 8.0% (n=32) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 76% of students aware that Human Rights have been included in the India Constitution in the form of fundamental rights and directive principles of State policy but still many around 24% of them are not aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e. 48.0% (n=192) believe that the Article 22 to Article 27 of Universal Declaration of Human Rights by UNO comprise of civil and political rights where 20.7% (n=83) respondents don't believe the same and 31.2% (n=125) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 79% of students still don't aware that the Article 22 to Article 27 of Universal Declaration of Human Rights by UNO comprise of civil and political rights and 21% of them are aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e. 37.0% (n=148) don't believe that the International Human Rights Day is celebrated on 5th May where 34.5% (n=138) respondents believe the same and 28.5% (n=114) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 63% of students don't aware that the International Human Rights Day is celebrated on 10th December and only 37% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 45.7% (n=183) don't believe that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is not a legal binding for the member countries of United Nations (UN) for promoting and protecting human rights where 35.7% (n=143) respondents believe the same and 18.5% (n=74) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 64% of students don't aware that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is a legal binding for the member countries of United Nations (UN) for promoting and protecting human rights and only 36% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 64.5% (n=258) don't believe that Parents have no right to choose the kind of education for their young children where 29.0% (n=116) respondents believe the same and 6.5% (n=26) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 65% of students aware that Parents have right to choose the kind of education for their young children but still many around 35% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 81.7% (n=327) believe that we have certain rights from our birth by virtue of being human where 12.5% (n=50) respondents don't believe the same and 5.7% (n=23) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 82% of students aware that we have certain rights from our birth by virtue of being human but still many around 18% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 69.0% (n=276) don't believe that the children who have got birth due to illegal or immoral relations between male and female are not entitle for social security under human rights where 15.5% (n=62) respondents believe the same and also 15.5% (n=62) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 69% of students aware that the children who have got birth due to illegal or immoral relations between male and female are entitle for social security under human rights but still many around 31% of them don't aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 51.0% (n=204) believe that fixation of maximum working hours per day in a private job/occupation is a part of human rights where 40.2% (n=161) respondents don't believe the same and 8.7% (n=35) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 60% of students don't aware that fixation of maximum working hours per day in a private job/occupation is a part of human rights but still many around 40% of them aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 50.2% (n=201) believe that it is the responsibility of the State that no individual should be debarred of human rights where 31.2% (n=125) respondents don't believe the same and 18.5% (n=74) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that more than 50% of students aware that it is the responsibility of the State that no individual should be debarred of human rights but still almost equal many around 50% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 83.0% (n=332) believe that the Human Rights are requisite for maintain dignity of people where 10.2% (n=41) respondents are undecided the same and 6.7% (n=27) respondents don't believe.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 83% of students aware that the Human Rights are requisite for maintain dignity of people but still many around 17% of them are not aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e. 35.2% (n=141) believe that the people cannot be debarred of their human rights even in the situation of anarchism in a country or a state where 33.5% (n=134) respondents are undecided the same and 31.2% (n=125) respondents don't believe.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 65% of students don't aware that the people cannot be debarred of their human rights even in the situation of anarchism in a country or a state but still many around 35% of them aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 69.7% (n=279) don't believe that the Child Labour does not fall under the purview of human rights where 18.5% (n=74) respondents believe the same and also 11.7% (n=47) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 70% of students aware that the Child Labour falls under the purview of human rights but still many around 30% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 76.5% (n=306) believe that Human Rights are conditioned to make us realize about our social responsibilities where 16.2% (n=65) respondents don't believe the same and 7.2% (n=29) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 77% of students aware that Human Rights are conditioned to make us realize about our social responsibilities but still many around 23% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 51.0% (n=204) believe that one person can join only one political party or one association at one time where 32.7% (n=131) respondents don't believe the same and 16.2% (n=65) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 67% of students don't aware that one person can join only one political party or one association at one time but still many around 33% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 60.0% (n=240) don't believe that the nationality or citizenship cannot be claimed as a human right where 25.2% (n=101) respondents believe the same and also 14.7% (n=59) respondents are undecided the same.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 60 % of students aware that the nationality or citizenship can be claimed as a human right but still many around 40% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 69.7% (n=279) believe that we are free to perform any work which does not restrict the freedom of other where 24.5% (n=98) respondents don't believe the same and 5.7% (n=23) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 70% of students aware that we are free to perform any work which does not restrict the freedom of other but still many around 30% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 56.2% (n=225) don't believe that the rights to choose own life partner and to get married does not come under human rights where 33.5% (n=137) respondents believe the same and also 9.5% (n=38) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 56% of students aware that the rights to choose own life partner and to get married comes under human rights but still many around 44% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 75.7% (n=303) believe that the equal pay for equal work is a part of human rights where 12.5% (n=50)

respondents don't believe the same and 11.7% (n=47) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 76% of students aware that the equal pay for equal work is a part of human rights but still many around 24% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 39.7% (n=159) believe that the action taken by police or armed forces against general public in the national interest fall outside the domain of human rights where 30.5% (n=122) respondents are undecided the same and 29.7% (n=119) respondents don't believe.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 70% of students don't aware that the action taken by police or armed forces against general public in the national interest does not fall outside the domain of human rights but still many around 30% of them aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 82.0% (n=328) don't believe that the police can arrest any person at any time without giving any reason where 12.7% (n=51) respondents believe the same and also 5.2% (n=21) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 82% of students aware that the police can't arrest any person at any time without giving any reason but still many around 18% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 60.0% (n=240) believe that to keep a person in custody for long time without any trial by the court is a violation of human rights where 26.0% (n=104) respondents don't believe the same and 14.0% (n=56) respondents are undecided the same.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 60% of students aware that to keep a person in custody for long time without any trial by the court is a violation of human rights but still many around 40% of them are not aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e. 46.5% (n=186) don't believe that a person put into the prison for criticizing the government is not a violation of human rights where 28.2% (n=113) respondents believe the same and also 25.2% (n=101) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 53% of students not aware that a person put into the prison for criticizing the government is not a violation of human rights and 47% of them are aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e. 45.0% (n=180) don't believe that the death of people on account of hunger or starvation falls outside the purview of human rights where 31.2% (n=125) respondents believe the same and also 23.7% (n=95) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 55% of students don't aware that the death of people on account of hunger or starvation falls outside the purview of human rights and 45% of them are aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e. 46.5% (n=186) don't believe that a house-owner refusing to rent his house to a person belonging to other state, does not violate human rights where 33.5% (n=134) respondents believe the same and also 20.0% (n=80) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 53% of students don't aware that a house-owner refusing to rent his house to a person belonging to other state, does not violate human rights 47% of them aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e.45.7% (n=183) don't believe that the human rights are not violated when the wages/salary of workers are kept low in a country to enhance foreign investment where 32.0% (n=128) respondents believe the same and also 22.2% (n=89) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 54% of students aware that the human rights are not violated when the wages/salary of workers are kept low in a country to enhance foreign investment and only around 46% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.55.5% (n=222) don't believe that the no violation of human rights takes place when a person of some specific race/religion is not appointed on a job where 26.0% (n=104) respondents believe the same and also 18.5% (n=74) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 56% of students aware that the violation of human rights takes place when a person of some specific race/religion is not appointed on a job but still many around 44% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.59.2% (n=237) don't believe that the some teenagers want to go to a club but the manager of the club does not allow them to enter because it is the rule of the club that teenagers can go to club only on Tuesday. This is violation of human rights of teenagers where 29.0% (n=116) respondents believe the same and also 11.7% (n=47) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 71% of students don't aware that the some teenagers want to go to a club but the manager of the club does not allow them to enter because it is the rule of the club that teenagers can go to club only on Tuesday. This is not violation of human rights of teenagers but still many around 29% of them aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.51.0% (n=204) believe that the person belonging to Sikh community was not given appointment in a security agency because the rule of the agency is that the security personnel's should be clean shaven. This is violation of human rights where 30.5% (n=122) respondents don't believe the same and 18.5% (n=74) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 51% of students aware that the person belonging to Sikh community was not given appointment in a security agency because the rule of the agency is that the security personnel's should be clean shaven. This is violation of human rights but still many around 49% of them are not aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e.41.0% (n=164) don't believe that a house-owner room available for hiring on rent basis but he wants to rent these rooms to only married person. This is a violation of human rights of unmarried individuals where 40.5% (n=162) respondents believe the same and also 18.5% (n=74) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 59% of students don't aware that a house-owner room available for hiring on rent

basis but he wants to rent these rooms to only married person. This is a violation of human rights of unmarried individuals and only around 41% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.73.5% (n=294) believe that the child was not given admission in a school because he is physically handicapped. This is the violation of the child's rights where 18.5% (n=74) respondents don't believe the same and 8.0% (n=32) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 74% of students aware that the child was not given admission in a school because he is physically handicapped. This is the violation of the child's rights but still many around 26% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.51.0% (n=204) believe that an employee, for making his religious prayers, was not given leave (without pay) by his senior officer although it would not affect the work of the company. This is a violation of human rights where 32.7% (n=131) respondents don't believe the same and also 16.2% (n=65) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 51% of students aware that the employee, for making his religious prayers, was not given leave (without pay) by his senior officer although it would not affect the work of the company. This is a violation of human rights but still many around 49% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.51.0% (n=204) believe that the women are restricted to enter liquor / beer bar. This is a violation of human rights of women where 33.5% (n=134) respondents don't believe the same and 15.5% (n=62) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 51% of students aware that the women are restricted to enter liquor / beer bar. This is a violation of human rights of women but still many around 49% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.62.2% (n=249) believe that in a private institution, the salary of a women for fifteen days was deducted by her employers because she remained absent from her duties as she gave birth to a baby. This is the violation of those women's rights where 29.7% (n=119) respondents don't believe the same and 8.0% (n=32) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 62% of students aware that in a private institution, the salary of a women for fifteen days was deducted by her employers because she remained absent from her duties as she gave birth to a baby. This is the violation of those women's rights but still many around 38% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.41.2% (n=165) don't believe that an employee was issued order by the employers to retire because he had attained an age of 65 years. But the employee says that he is still fit for the job for which he also produces an authenticated medical report. This is a violation of human rights to give forced retirement to the employee where 38.0% (n=152) respondents believe the same and also 20.7% (n=83) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 59% of students don't aware that the employee was issued order by the employers to retire because he had attained an age of 65 years. But the

employee says that he is still fit for the job for which he also produces an authenticated medical report. This is a violation of human rights to give forced retirement to the employee and only around 41% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.52.5% (n=210) believe that the child was refused to give admission in a school because his parents did not have his birth certificate. This is a violation of human rights where 32.7% (n=131) respondents don't believe the same and 14.7% (n=59) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 53% of students aware that the child was refused to give admission in a school because his parents did not have his birth certificate. This is a violation of human rights but still many around 47% of them are not aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e.45.7% (n=183) believe that the public get harassed and has to face many troubles due to a number of checkpoints on the road created by the government to curb drug smuggling in the region. This is a violation of human rights of general public where 38.0% (n=152) respondents don't believe the same and 16.2% (n=65) respondents are undecided the same.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 62% of students don't aware that the public get harassed and has to face many troubles due to a number of checkpoints on the road created by the government to curb drug smuggling in the region. This is a violation of human rights of general public and only around 38% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.60.5% (n=242) believe that the People of any community are provoked by other religion's people to change their religion. This is a case of violation of human rights where 32.2% (n=129) respondents don't believe the same and 7.2% (n=29) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 61% of students aware that the People of any community are provoked by other religion's people to change their religion. This is a case of violation of human rights but still many around 39% of them are not aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e.47.2% (n=189) believe that the police had to face a number of problems in traffic control because of a rally at a public place organized against price hike and corruption. So, the use of tear gas by the police to disperse this rally does come under violation of human rights where 29.7% (n=119) respondents don't believe the same and 23.0% (n=92) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 53% of students don't aware that the police had to face a number of problems in traffic control because of a rally at a public place organized against price hike and corruption. So, the use of tear gas by the police to disperse this rally does come under violation of human rights and only around 47% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.45.7% (n=183) don't believe that the acquisition of the private land by the government in the name of development and against the willingness of land owners is not a violation of human rights where 35.0% (n=140) respondents believe the same and 19.2% (n=77) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 54% of students don't aware that that the acquisition of the private land by the government in the name of development and against the willingness of land owners is a violation of human rights and only around 46% of them are aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.56.2% (n=225) believe that the non-white individual was not given appointment as manager in a reputed industry in North India because he is a South India. South India has the right to make appeal before the court where 23.7% (n=95) respondents don't believe the same and 20.0% (n=80) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 56% of students aware that the non-white individual was not given appointment as manager in a reputed industry in North India because he is a South India. South India has the right to make appeal before the court but still many around 44% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 61.5% (n=246) don't believe that the make people believe about as well as encourage them for HIV/AIDS testing is a violation of human rights where 29.7% (n=119) respondents believe the same and also 8.7% (n=35) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 62% of students aware that that the make people believe about as well as encourage them for HIV/AIDS testing is a violation of human rights but still many around 38% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.51.7% (n=207) don't believe that the human rights are not violated when a legal action is initiated by the institution with the help of police against the students who were agitating peacefully for fulfilment of their demands where 26.7% (n=107) respondents believe the same and also 21.5% (n=86) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 52% of students aware that the human rights are violated when a legal action is initiated by the institution with the help of police against the students who were agitating peacefully for fulfilment of their demands but still many around % of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.78.7% (n=315) believe that the involvement in the acts of ragging in an education institution is a violation of human rights where 15.5% (n=62) respondents don't believe the same and 5.7% (n=23) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 79% of students aware that the involvement in the acts of ragging in an education institution is a violation of human rights but still many around 21% of them are not aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e. 37.5% (n=150) don't believe that the human rights are not violated when a terrorist under trial in the court, is kept in jail with handcuffs and irons on his body where 32.7% (n=131) respondents believe the same and also 29.7% (n=119) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 62% of students don't aware that but still many around 38% of them aware the same.

Most of respondents i.e.37.5% (n=150) believe that the human rights are violated when young children are engaged in manual

works in restaurants, dhabas, shops etc. where 32.7% (n=131) respondents don't believe the same and 29.7% (n=119) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 62% of students don't aware that the human rights are violated when young children are engaged in manual works in restaurants, dhabas, shops etc. but still many around 38% of them aware the same.

Majority of respondents i.e.57.7% (n=231) don't believe that to provide employment opportunities to each and every citizen of a country by the government is not a human right where 29.0% (n=116) respondents believe the same and also 13.2% (n=53) respondents are undecided.

So, Researcher understood that majority around 58% of students aware that to provide employment opportunities to each and every citizen of a country by the government is a human right but still many around 42% of them do not aware the same.

Conclusion

To sum up, the researcher has tried to assess the level of knowledge and understanding of Human Rights among Youth especially students. The Students are known about many of Human Rights and their situations although the their level of knowledge must be improved because as data mentioned they did not aware of many things of human Rights and it is a sign of bad things of our education and society. Our society, Government, NGO and education system etc. have to take initiate for the development of such important subject for the development of youth and nation as well.

Reference

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